

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Amino-1:3:4-furodiazole (I, R=H).—Formylthiosemicarbazide (10 g. in 400 c.c. of alcohol) was boiled with lead oxide (100 g.) for about 20 hours. The black lead sulphide was filtered off and the filtrate concentrated when a white crystalline solid was obtained. This was crystallised from water in white rectangles, m.p. 155°. (Yield very poor). (Found: N, 49.53. $C_2H_3ON_3$ requires N, 49.41 per cent.). It is soluble in water and alcohol. A solution of the furodiazole in strong hydrochloric acid turned light yellow on the addition of sodium nitrite solution.

2-Amino-5-methyl-1:3:4-furodiazole (I, R=Me).—Acetylthiosemicarbazide (10 g. in 400 c.c. of alcohol) was boiled with lead oxide (80 g.) for 24 hours. The filtrate from the lead sulphide on concentration deposited a white solid which was crystallised from a mixture of water and alcohol in white rectangles, m.p. 183°. (Found: N, 42.56. $C_3H_5ON_3$ requires N, 42.42 per cent.). It is soluble in hot water and in alcohol. Its solution in hydrochloric acid turned yellow with a solution of sodium nitrite.

The acetyl derivative crystallised from alcohol in yellowish-white needles, m.p. 180°. (Found: N, 29.69. $C_5H_7O_2N_3$ requires N, 29.79 per cent.).

2-Amino-5-phenyl-1:3:4-furodiazole (I, R=Ph).—Benzoylthiosemicarbazide (10 g. in 400 c.c. of alcohol) was boiled with lead oxide (60 g.) for 24 hours. The solution after the removal of lead sulphide was concentrated when white prismatic crystals were obtained in good yield. Recrystallised from alcohol it melts at 245° (decomp.). (Found: N, 26.22. $C_8H_7ON_3$ requires N, 26.09 per cent.). It is insoluble in cold and slightly soluble in hot water and readily soluble in hot alcohol. From hot dilute hydrochloric acid solution the hydrochloride of the base separated out which decomposes at 175.6°.

2-Acetylamino-5-phenyl-1:3:4-furodiazole was crystallised from water in white needles, m.p. 223°. (Found: N, 20.80. $C_{10}H_9O_2N_3$ requires N, 20.69 per cent.).

2-Benzoylamino-5-phenyl-1:3:4-furodiazole.—It was prepared by boiling a pyridine solution of the diazole with benzoyl chloride. It crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 203°. (Found: N, 15.97. $C_{15}H_{11}O_2N_3$ requires N, 15.85 per cent.).

2-Nitrosoamino-5-phenyl-1:3:4-furodiazole (II).—To a suspension of aminophenylfurodiazole hydrochloride in dilute hydrochloric acid,

an aqueous solution of sodium nitrite was slowly added with continuous stirring. A yellowish-white mass soluble in caustic alkalis was thus obtained. It separated from alcohol in light yellow crystals which turned black at 103°. (Found: N, 29.85. $C_8H_6O_2N_4$ requires N, 29.47 per cent.). It is insoluble in water, easily soluble in ether and in hot alcohol.

2-Benzylidenehydrazino-5-phenyl-1:3:4-furodiazole.—The above nitroso-amine was suspended in water to which zinc dust was added. This was then cooled and treated with a dilute acetic acid solution. The mixture was allowed to stand for 6 hours with frequent shaking when the nitroso-compound gradually went into solution. The solution was filtered from the zinc dust and shaken up with benzaldehyde. A white solid was thus obtained which was pressed on a porous plate to remove the adhering aldehyde and then crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 243° (decomp.). (Found: N, 21.35. $C_{15}H_{12}ON_4$ requires N, 21.21 per cent.).

It is insoluble in water, slightly soluble in cold and readily soluble in hot alcohol. When the benzylidene compound was boiled with dilute hydrochloric acid for 10 minutes, smell of benzaldehyde was noticed which was removed by passing steam. The clear solution was then evaporated until a crystalline solid was obtained. This was filtered, washed with alcohol and crystallised from hot water, m.p. 208°. This is the hydrochloride of a base, the latter being obtained by treating an aqueous solution of the hydrochloride with ammonia. The white precipitate was crystallised from aqueous alcohol, m.p. 152°. On analysis it gave 47.55% nitrogen. It is not the expected hydrazinofurodiazole but some other compound.

5:5'-Diphenyl-2:2'-azo-1:3:4-furodiazole (IV).—A solution of 2-amino-1:3:4-furodiazole or its 5-methyl derivative turns yellow on treatment with calcium hypochlorite solution, probably due to the formation of the corresponding azo-compound. In the case of the phenyl derivative the azo-compound was isolated as follows: An alcoholic solution of aminophenylfurodiazole was gently warmed with an excess of a concentrated aqueous solution of calcium hypochlorite. The yellow precipitate thus obtained was washed successively with water and alcohol and was crystallised from nitrobenzene as an orange, crystalline powder, m.p. 329-30°. (Found: N, 26.54. $C_{16}H_{10}O_2N_6$ requires N, 26.42 per cent.). It is insoluble in water, alcohol and ether; slightly soluble in hot acetic acid. When the alcoholic suspension of the azo-compound was allowed to stand over-

night with an alcoholic solution of ammonium sulphide a colourless precipitate of the hydrazo-compound (V) was obtained which melted at 283° and turned reddish-yellow with calcium hypochlorite solution.

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